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*SUSTAINABLE ENTREPRENEURSHIP PRACTICES IN COCOA CULTURE:
EVIDENCE FROM A CASE STUDY¹*

**PRÁTICAS DE EMPREENDEDORISMO SUSTENTÁVEL NA CULTURA
CACAUUEIRA: EVIDÊNCIAS DE UM ESTUDO DE CASO**

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable Entrepreneurship (SE) is widely discussed in the literature as a form of entrepreneurial activity aimed at integrating environmental, social, and economic dimensions into its core activities. At the same time, the types of practices developed, as well as their contribution and alignment with the sustainable values of the business, are topics that deserve further exploration. In order to address this gap, the present study aims to analyze sustainable practices developed by a small enterprise engaged in cocoa cultivation in the Carajás region of Pará. This region, notable for its significant Gross Domestic Product (GDP), has an economy heavily dependent on mining activities and faces substantial challenges in the sustainable development arena, making it a relevant context for this research. The results emphasize that although some practices predominantly belong to one specific dimension of sustainability, they still generate positive impacts on the others, albeit in a more subtle manner. As a practical contribution, the study reveals that logistical and training elements can represent considerable challenges in the implementation of sustainable practices in remote regions, demanding more incisive and constant action on the part of entrepreneurs.

Keywords: sustainable entrepreneurship, sustainability practices, cocoa culture, Carajás region.

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RESUMO

O Empreendedorismo Sustentável (ES) é amplamente disseminado na literatura como uma forma de atuação empreendedora orientada a integrar dimensões ambiental, social e econômica em suas atividades centrais. Ao mesmo tempo, os tipos de práticas desenvolvidas, bem como, a contribuição e o alinhamento destas aos valores sustentáveis do negócio são temas que merecem maior aprofundamento. Tendo em vista auxiliar no atendimento a esta demanda, o presente estudo tem por objetivo central analisar práticas sustentáveis desenvolvidas por uma pequena empresa adepta a cultura cacaueteira na região de Carajás, no Pará. Esta região, proeminente por seu expressivo Produto Interno Bruto (PIB), apresenta uma economia altamente dependente da atividade mineral e enfrenta desafios significativos na arena sustentável sendo, portanto, considerada um contexto relevante para desenvolvimento desta pesquisa. Os resultados alcançados reforçam que embora algumas práticas pertençam de forma preponderante a uma ou outra dimensão da sustentabilidade, esta não deixa de ocasionar impactos positivos nas demais, ainda que de forma mais tímida. Como contribuição prática, o estudo revela que elementos logísticos e de capacitação podem representar desafios consideráveis na implementação de práticas sustentáveis em regiões remotas, demandando atuação mais incisiva e constante por parte dos empreendedores.

Palavras-chave: empreendedorismo sustentável, práticas de sustentabilidade, cultura cacaueteira, região de Carajás.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the emergence of increasingly severe social and environmental crises highlights the need for a proactive stance from the business sector. In response, different forms of action have been developed, among which Sustainable Entrepreneurship (SE) stands out (SCHALTEGGER; BECKMANN; HOCKERTS, 2018).

Understood as an innovative field that addresses contemporary socio-environmental needs, SE simultaneously encompasses economic, social, and environmental dimensions (SANTOS; TEIXEIRA, 2021), prioritizing organizational practices that seek transformation toward sustainability.

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Business models within this framework are not limited to mitigating negative environmental impacts but also aim to improve quality of life and offer tangible benefits to consumers and communities (SCHALTEGGER; LÜDEKE-FREUND; HANSEN, 2016). To this end, harmonizing economic growth with socio-environmental well-being constitutes a fundamental premise to be considered in the actions of sustainable entrepreneurs (HALDAR, 2019).

These individuals, also referred to as eco-entrepreneurs, are motivated by different factors (PARRISH, 2010) and face considerable challenges when trying to balance the dimensions of sustainability in their businesses (SANTOS; TEIXEIRA, 2021). This occurs because, in practice, establishing a profitable business capable of generating clear social and environmental benefits through its activities is a complex undertaking (YOUNG; TILLEY, 2009).

In order to address such challenges and enhance the benefits arising from sustainable entrepreneurship initiatives, it becomes relevant to deepen knowledge about these themes within the context in which they occur. In this sense, the present study has as its main objective to analyze sustainable practices developed by a small company engaged in cocoa cultivation in the Carajás region, in the state of Pará.

The Carajás region stands out for its high GDP per capita (the second highest in the country in 2021), driven mainly by copper and iron mining (IBGE, 2023). At the same time, an economy highly dependent on mining activities faces significant sustainability and resilience challenges, since mineral extraction causes serious environmental impacts, such as biodiversity loss and the destruction of Amazonian vegetation (MALERBA; MILANEZ; WANDERLEY, 2012). In addition, the lack of economic diversification makes the region vulnerable to future problems, including unemployment and financial instability, as mineral resources are depleted and mining companies potentially withdraw.

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In this scenario, cocoa cultivation and sustainable entrepreneurship emerge as promising alternatives to diversify Carajás' economy, offering a renewable source of income that is less dependent on mining. The expansion of cocoa farming, combined with sustainable practices, can stimulate local development, strengthen food security, and create opportunities for small entrepreneurs.

Beyond this introductory section, the study is structured as follows: first, the theoretical framework is presented, followed by the methodological procedures employed to achieve the proposed objective. Next, a description of the study context is provided, followed by evidence related to benefits and challenges in the social, environmental, and economic dimensions. Finally, concluding remarks are offered.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Sustainable entrepreneurship

As a field of research, Sustainable Entrepreneurship (SE) presents a wide range of definitions in the literature (see, for example: COHEN; WINN, 2007; HOCKERTS; WÜSTENHAGEN, 2010; SCHALTEGGER; HANSEN; LÜDEKE-FREUND, 2016). For the purposes of developing this study, this business practice is understood as the process of discovering, evaluating, and exploiting economic opportunities present in market failures, including those that are environmentally relevant (DEAN; MCMULLEN, 2007).

By jointly addressing environmental, social, and economic dimensions in the business context, sustainable entrepreneurs go beyond the traditional view oriented exclusively toward profit seeking, contributing significantly to quality of

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life and environmental preservation in the regions where they operate (TILLEY; YOUNG, 2009; SCHALTEGGER; BECKMANN; HOCKERTS, 2018).

In this context, for an organization to be considered sustainable, it is essential that the activities carried out integrate and benefit, in some way, environmental and social dimensions alongside economic aspects (PARRISH, 2010).

Among the actions to be undertaken, one may mention the development of new sustainable products and services with high market potential (SCHALTEGGER, 2002; KRAUS et al., 2017), the reduction of pollutant emissions, the continuous search for more environmentally friendly opportunities (SCHAPER, 2002), the use of renewable resources, as well as activities aimed at waste reduction and recycling (HALL; DANEKE; LENOX, 2010).

In an effort to define probable activities to be carried out by sustainable companies, Schlange (2006) established criteria across the three dimensions, as presented in Chart 1.

It is worth noting that the criteria presented in Chart 1 are not exhaustive, but they may offer a relevant analytical lens for investigating sustainable practices in the business context.

For this reason, in the present study and with the aim of achieving the proposed objective, this framework will be used as a theoretical background to analyze the actions of a company dedicated to the production and commercialization of fine chocolates in the Carajás region, Pará.

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Chart 1. Sustainable Entrepreneurship Practices

	DIMENSION	INDICATORS	PRACTICE
ECONOMIC		Acquisition	Use of materials from regional suppliers
		Persistence	Clear prospects for the company's long-term development
		Growth Potential	Economic objectives of growth, investment, and innovation orientation
		Mission	Sustainability orientation as an integral part of the company's value system
		Identification	Employees share a common understanding of sustainability objectives
		Cooperation	Long-standing relationships with local and regional partners
ENVIRONMENTAL		Transportation	Use of environmentally friendly means of transport
		Waste	Alternative energy sources and efficient use of energy consumed
		Emissions	Reduction of waste emissions and material waste
		Production Process	Reduction of emission levels, elimination of toxicity
		Product	Ecological management of production processes
SOCIAL/ ETHICAL		Equal Rights	Addressing gender issues and generating jobs for people with disabilities
		Participation	Participative management in business objectives, support for community activities
		Personnel	Active development of employee skills, fair reward schemes
		Work Environment	Offering safe conditions and health programs for employees
		Regional Integration	Exchange of experiences with local/regional economic cultural activities
		Communication	Honesty in transparent information to the public about business activities

Source: SCHLANGE (2006).

In order to better understand the research scenario, this is presented further in the following sub-item.

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RESEARCH MACRO CONTEXT – THE CARAJÁS REGION

The Carajás region is known as one of the main areas of mining activity in Brazil. The municipality of Canaã dos Carajás and its surroundings stand out as important mining hubs, driving the economy of the Southeast Pará mesoregion.

With regard to the analysis of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) divided by the number of inhabitants, Canaã dos Carajás has consolidated its prominent position within the state of Pará. In 2021, the municipality ranked first on this indicator, showing a remarkable GDP per capita - the second highest in the country. The value reached R\$ 894,000, according to data from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE, 2023).

This performance places Canaã dos Carajás in a privileged position in the national economic landscape, demonstrating the strength of the municipality in Pará as well as its capacity for significant growth over short periods. However, per capita household income in the state of Pará reveals a striking contrast.

As shown in Figure 1, Pará's per capita income is 36.1% lower than the national average and 4.3% lower than the average for the Amazon region. In addition, between 2012 and 2022, Pará demonstrated a notable capacity for economic growth, with an 11.1% increase in per capita household income.

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Figure 1. Per capita household income (Brazil, Legal Amazon and Pará)

Source: Amazônia legal em dados 2024.

This growth significantly surpassed that observed in the rest of Brazil, which was only 1.6%, and also exceeded the 6.6% growth recorded in the remainder of the Amazon region. This performance highlights the state's resilience and economic potential despite the challenges faced. Pará's ability to surpass regional and national growth averages underscores the importance of understanding the factors that drove this economic rise, especially in the context of Canaã dos Carajás, which stands out not only in mineral extraction but also as an example of potential economic diversification through the bioindustry of fine chocolates.

Such a scenario highlights the importance of investigating and understanding the factors that contributed to this remarkable economic performance in the Carajás region in 2021, representing a relevant point to be explored in the context of the present academic work. What occurs is that Canaã dos Carajás and nearby municipalities - such as Parauapebas, Água Azul do Norte, Curionópolis, Eldorado dos Carajás, Ourilândia do Norte, and Tucumã - form a vital core for mineral exploration in the area, benefiting from the royalties

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generated by the sector, which enable mining municipalities to increase their per capita revenues (AGÊNCIA PARÁ, 2023).

By examining the behavior of the regional economy not only from the perspective of output generated by economic activity but also through demand formation, the prominent role played by investments in certain sectors and subsectors becomes evident.

Understanding local economic dynamics, the sectors that have driven this growth, and the impacts of this development on the community can provide insight into the municipality's socioeconomic reality. Although these activities have played a crucial role in local economic development, the lack of diversification represents a challenge in terms of sustainability and resilience.

Mining activity and environmental sustainability are antagonistic processes. Even with the technical and technological resources currently available, mineral extraction still causes major socio-environmental impacts. The extraction process results in the destruction of vast areas of vegetation in the Amazon, contributing to a considerable decline in biodiversity (MALERBA; MILANEZ; WANDERLEY, 2012). Therefore, there is a need to seek alternatives that not only boost the local economy but also promote sustainable practices.

However, the economy of the city of Canaã dos Carajás is currently dependent on mineral exploitation, especially copper and iron ore. Yet these are finite resources, and such dependence may, in the future, lead to serious social problems as mining companies and contractors withdraw from the city, generating unemployment, financial instability, and a significant population decline.

The initiative to establish a fine-chocolate industry using Amazonian cocoa in the region represents a crucial step toward economic diversification. In addition to offering a new source of income for family farmers, this strategy aims

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to supply part of the regional chocolate market. However, this pursuit should not be solely commercial, but also environmental and social.

Thus, having presented the research context and highlighted its relevance, the following section describes the methodological path undertaken.

METHODOLOGY

The present study adopts a qualitative approach with a descriptive purpose (YIN, 2010). Qualitative studies deal with data that cannot be quantified, relying on inductive analysis and focusing on the interpretation of issues related to the research and the attribution of meanings (CRESWELL; CRESWELL, 2018). In this research, the qualitative approach was applied through an analysis focused on sustainable practices developed within the context of a small company.

In turn, the descriptive purpose provides a detailed description of the phenomenon under study (YIN, 2010), which was addressed by identifying and describing the benefits and challenges present in the investigated context.

For its operationalization, a single case study strategy was adopted, involving the selection of a specific object of study, which may be a person, a program, an institution, a company, or a group of individuals who share a common environment and experiences (STAKE, 1994). The case chosen for this research was a company engaged in chocolate production and in the development of cocoa cultivation in the Carajás region, in the state of Pará. For confidentiality purposes, the investigated case will be referred to as Company X.

For data collection, the following techniques were used: (i) direct observation, (ii) document analysis, and (iii) semi-structured interviews. The interviews took place between December 2023 and March 2024 with the partner-owners of Company X. Chart 2 presents the profile of the individuals interviewed.

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Chart 1. Profile of individuals interviewed

Participant	Gender	Professional Background	Age
Entrepreneur A	Male	Agricultural Engineer	29
Entrepreneur B	Male	Gastronomy	28
Entrepreneur C	Male	Agricultural Engineer	28

Fonte: Dados da pesquisa (2023)

The direct observation technique was carried out through on-site visits to the chocolate factory alongside the partner-entrepreneurs of Company X and some farmers who work with cocoa in the region. Finally, the document analysis technique was based on organizational records generated between 2020 and 2023 as a result of participation in an entrepreneurship education program that included the Acceleration of Sustainable Businesses in the Amazon. In addition, other available documents were consulted, such as managerial reports, media materials, videos, and public presentations related to the company.

An analysis of these documents was conducted, covering their history, sustainability projects, as well as other business-related records. This analysis complemented the information obtained from the interviews, providing a deeper understanding of the history and context examined.

RESULTS

This section will present the results of the present study, analyzed in light of sustainable entrepreneurship approaches, with the purpose of achieving the initially outlined objective.

Micro context of the research - company X

By definition, sustainable enterprises must involve actions that integrally address the environmental, social, and economic triad (SCHALTEGGER; HANSEN; LÜDEKE-FREUND, 2016). In businesses of this nature, a sense of responsibility toward the natural environment, customers, and the surrounding

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population can be considered a guiding principle, implemented through the exploration of market gaps and/or opportunities regarded as unsustainable (DEAN; MCMULLEN, 2007).

In the specific context of Company X, evidence expressed in the statement of Entrepreneur B (2023) highlights the business's intentions not only to benefit partners, the environment, and the local population, but also to promote cocoa culture in a sustainable manner:

The company seeks to be a pioneer in cocoa transformation in the Carajás region as a source of income for the company, its employees, and its suppliers, transforming the entire production chain and, above all, the lives of local producers. The solution we offer involves producing chocolates that not only satisfy the palate but also fill an existing market gap, providing an authentic representation of local biodiversity. (Entrepreneur B, 2023)

Structurally, the economy of the Legal Amazon can be described by its regional specialization in the production of low value-added agricultural and mineral commodities, with a high carbon emissions impact (NOBRE; FRASSON; GENIN, 2023). However, Company X adopts a different approach by introducing cocoa cultivation areas:

By introducing cocoa cultivation areas, the team seeks not only to diversify the economy but to do so sustainably. The production of fine chocolates not only adds value to the product but also emphasizes the importance of environmental conservation, responsible agricultural practices, and fair trade. (Entrepreneur C, 2023)

This initiative seeks not only to ensure the quality and origin of the raw materials obtained but also to disseminate sustainable practices and establish a fair supply chain with local producers, highlighting an inclusive and responsible orientation within the business.

Regarding the creation of the business, it is relevant to note that Company X emerged within an entrepreneurship education program aimed at fostering innovation and supporting income generation to train young entrepreneurs focused on sustainability and guide some of them toward starting

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their own companies. The initiative to create the program came from a mining company operating in the region, which benefited not only Company X but also eight other companies practicing sustainable entrepreneurship and demonstrating the potential to generate a positive local impact.

During the program, the entrepreneurs underwent an immersion journey into the social, economic, institutional, ethno-cultural, and environmental dimensions of the Amazon, receiving instruction on the business potential of the forest, biodiversity, and agroforestry systems. In addition, they received training on new economic models (circular economy, creative economy) and sustainable businesses, including methodologies based on cutting-edge concepts such as design thinking, CANVAS, the hero's journey, and behavioral psychology.

Throughout the program's mentoring process, the team faced challenges and went through a phase of refining the initial idea. The close guidance of mentors was essential for aligning the company's vision with local objectives and the principles of sustainable entrepreneurship. The identification of the opportunity in Amazonian chocolate production sought not only to differentiate the product in terms of quality but also to integrate sustainable practices at every stage of the production chain. In line with the premises of sustainable enterprises (SCHLANGE, 2006), according to Entrepreneur B, Company X established as its vision the creation of a brand capable of valuing local potential while respecting relevant socio-environmental aspects.

Our vision goes beyond chocolate production; it is about creating a brand committed to socio-environmental responsibility and that celebrates the uniqueness of Carajás. (Entrepreneur B, 2023)

In the program, the entrepreneurs participated in practical workshops covering several areas crucial to the creation and development of their companies. These sessions included legal, accounting, financial, marketing and sales, production, and management aspects, providing a comprehensive understanding of the main operational routines in each of these areas.

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Under the guidance, monitoring, and mentoring provided, the initial business idea - once only a concept - was shaped until it took physical form. At the time this research was conducted, Company X's team consisted of five members, including a rural producer, an agronomist, and a gastronomy specialist, all of whom were interviewed.

It is worth noting that each member contributed specific skills from their respective fields, and collaboration among them drove the development of a chocolate factory that encompassed everything from support for local cocoa cultivation to final packaging and product sales.

Given this context, the company not only seeks to prosper economically but also to play an active role in fostering and preserving cocoa culture in the region, having received recognition for its innovative and sustainable approach. Having presented the context of Company X, the following subsection analyzes some of the practices developed within this business.

Sustainable practices developed at Company X

Within the scope of sustainable enterprises, the social dimension represents the contribution a business provides to members of the local community. Actions in this dimension may be carried out in different ways; however, in all cases, they result in a positive social impact in the environment in which the business operates (PARRISH, 2010).

According to evidence expressed in the statements of Entrepreneurs A and C, in addition to valuing local production and providing support to producers, Company X does not limit itself to using raw materials sustainably. Instead, it actively seeks social sustainability by valuing the labor of local producers through the creation of a project called the "Integration System."

One of the main key points (of the business) is the creation of the integration system project with farmers, whose primary objective is to generate income for them, preventing rural exodus and ensuring

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income for rural workers, while at the same time securing quality products for the company at viable prices. (Entrepreneur A, 2023)
In this system, we seek not only to have farmers as suppliers of raw materials, but also as partners, making the company an agent of environmental and socioeconomic development for the region. (Entrepreneur C, 2023)

The effort to integrate members of the local community into the core of the business - establishing long-term partnerships and generating profitability for both parties - aligns with the criteria concerning the provision of fair working conditions and the promotion of partnerships with local producers presented in Schlange (2006). Considering the relevance of family farming in cocoa production in Pará - which totaled 206,000 workers in 2023 (NOBRE; FRASSON; GENIN, 2023) - these actions can be considered relevant initiatives in the context of sustainable entrepreneurship.

Subsequently, regarding the environmental dimension, there is consensus that sustainable businesses seek to provide benefits to the natural environment in which they operate more directly and, if possible, to other locations in a more modest way (PARRISH, 2010).

As a result, actions of this nature may occur in different forms, including conscious energy consumption, environmental education initiatives, and the use of clean production processes, among others (SCHAPER, 2002). At Company X, the methodology adopted by the founders seeks to provide technical assistance and inputs so that new producers can implement and establish cocoa cultivation in the region in a clean, sustainable, and responsible manner.

To this end, within the aforementioned "Integration System Project," Company X adopts a proactive approach in seeking out villages and producer associations near Canaã. The selection of locations takes into account ease of access to main roads, aiming to optimize service logistics. As a result, interested farmers receive technical assistance to ensure efficient agricultural practices and

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are introduced to details about the factory, the importance of cocoa cultivation in the region, and the potential income per area dedicated to this crop.

According to evidence expressed in Entrepreneur A's statement (2023), the support provided through this project seeks especially to enable operational efficiency in the businesses while properly instructing producers on the best actions to be undertaken.

As this is a new crop to be implemented, many mistakes can be made in the initial phases, affecting final production and the establishment of the crop. With the company's help, these errors can be minimized, and the producer can benefit in the future by becoming more productive. (Entrepreneur A, 2023)

In Schlange (2006), the ecological management of production processes prioritizing clean sources is identified as a relevant environmental practice. In addition, the instructional process carried out by Company X with producers can be considered a significant environmental education initiative (SANTOS; TEIXEIRA, 2021), as it enables them to learn more about cocoa cultivation and understand the best techniques for its development.

Taking a closer look at Company X's "Integration System," it is worth noting that it encompasses several stages, beginning with the registration of producers and followed by detailed physical and physicochemical analyses of the area. In addition to environmental benefits achieved through production optimization, it also involves elements of the economic dimension, justified by the purchase of cocoa beans and the establishment of long-term commercial partnerships, as illustrated in Figure 2.

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Figure 2. Integration System Flowchart
Source: Original research results

The stages of the flowchart presented in Figure 2 show that, after (1) “Registration,” (2) “Physical Area Analysis” is carried out, comprising a detailed assessment of terrain and soil depth to determine the viability of the crop. Next, (3) “Physicochemical Area Analysis” is conducted, including soil sampling to evaluate fertility and provide a solid basis for implementation planning.

(4) “Planting Planning” and (5) “Crop Implementation” are phases that involve the economic dimension of the business through the definition of costs, the establishment of a schedule, and the possibility of initial capitalization through the temporary introduction of complementary crops, such as bananas or vegetables. At this stage, Company X relies on the support of public agencies, such as the Canaã Department of Agriculture, to ensure the proper supply of inputs - such as seedlings and fertilizers - to producers.

In addition, credit lines are explored with financial institutions and government agencies, aiming to facilitate producers’ access to financial resources that can drive the sustainable growth of cocoa production in the region.

For producers who already have established cocoa cultivation, Company X assumes responsibility for Fertilization and Pruning Planning, which are essential for optimizing cocoa production. Technical support is maintained

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through (6) the “Visit Schedule,” conducted monthly with partner producers. During these visits, the company performs the necessary analyses to monitor crop development, ensuring the long-term success of the partnership.

The final stage of the system is when the company carries out (7) the “Purchase of Beans” from partner producers. This not only strengthens commercial ties but also ensures a sustainable and consistent source of raw material for the production of high-quality chocolates. In this sense, the integration between Company X and local producers is essential for building a solid and sustainable production chain.

Chart 3 presents the SE practices mapped in the context of Company X, based on the framework provided by Schlange (2006). In addition, the initial framework is expanded through the description of other actions identified within the context of Company X.

Based on the evidence presented throughout this subsection, Company X can be seen as playing a significant leading role in the region, generating direct social, environmental, and economic impacts on the local population through its operations (SCHALTEGGER; BECKMANN; HOCKERTS, 2018). At the same time, as noted throughout this study, beyond the benefits arising from the implementation of SE, integrating the components of the triad may face significant challenges (TILLEY; YOUNG, 2009).

Among these, and considering the Amazon region - the focus area of this study - the limited operational efficiency of institutions and companies engaged in sustainable entrepreneurship, combined with a lack of strategic planning and coordination in integrated bioeconomy actions, may restrict the full exploration of this growth potential (UNDP, 2023).

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Chart 2. Sustainable Entrepreneurship Practices at Company X

	DIMENSION	PRACTICE	DESCRIPTION
ECONOMIC		Use of materials from regional suppliers	Company X uses raw materials from producers in the region, boosting the local economy and ensuring the quality of inputs through monitoring.
		Sustainable orientation as an integral part of the company's value system	The entrepreneurs demonstrate, through their statements, the strong sustainable focus in conducting the business.
		Long-standing relationships with local and regional partners	Company X seeks to assist, prioritize, and maintain extensive partnerships with local producers.
		Technical assistance and monitoring	Actions are carried out to instruct producers and promote the dissemination of best practices in cocoa farming, with a view to ensuring more efficient production.
ENVIRONMENTAL		Ecological management of production processes	Through the Integration System developed with producers, Company X disseminates sustainable practices aimed at improving the production process.
		Education and awareness of partners	Actions are carried out to instruct partner producers on the need for environmental care in cultivation practices.
SOCIAL/ ETHICAL		Participatory management in business objectives, support for community activities	Company X actively seeks out producers, triggering a chain of positive partnerships.
		Fostering local culture, leveraging the region's potential	Monitoring and consulting actions are carried out so that producers understand the potential of cocoa cultivation in the region.
		Promotion of citizenship	Through its actions, Company X generates income and helps promote the dignity of rural people.

Source: Original research results, based on SCHLANGE (2006).

Thus, in Company X, the logistical challenges faced due to the remote location of producers highlight the complexity of implementing sustainable practices in specific regional contexts. Added to this factor, the need to train suppliers and producers to adopt sustainable practices reveals obstacles that involve instilling a sense of sustainability in these partners, as well as the monitoring and control required to ensure process compliance.

The greatest challenge is reconciling management and implementing sustainable practices in everyday operations. Considering the

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distances to producers and logistical challenges, it is difficult to transfer knowledge to producers, ensure they put it into practice, and monitor production. (Entrepreneur A, 2023)

In addition to logistical and training challenges, the implementation of the sustainable practices plan also faces the significant issue of associated costs. The commitment to sustainability requires substantial investments in inputs, technical assistance, and other resources necessary to ensure the effective application of environmentally friendly practices. In this context, the need to control costs without compromising the quality and effectiveness of sustainable practices adds an additional layer of complexity to the process (HALDAR, 2019).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The present study aimed to analyze sustainable practices developed by a small company engaged in cocoa cultivation in the Carajás region, in the state of Pará. Based on the evidence collected, actions were identified that integrate the three dimensions of sustainable entrepreneurship - environmental, social, and economic - in a responsible and coordinated manner.

Beyond this aspect, the results suggest that although some practices predominantly belong to one dimension of sustainability, they still generate impacts on the others, even if more subtly. Thus, through the integration of the local community into its production process, consultancy and training initiatives, and long-term partnerships established with local producers, Company X is able to foster the local economy, promote citizenship among rural populations, and disseminate sound environmental practices in the region.

Although these results do not represent a novelty in the sustainable entrepreneurship literature, analyzing them in light of practical situations and in different contexts is relevant for shedding further light on the topic and providing new insights to the field. It becomes clear that the dimensions of sustainability

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can be addressed jointly and, even if not perfectly balanced, integrated within the business environment.

As a limitation, it is important to note that, as a single case study conducted in the specific context of the Amazon, the results presented here should not be considered analytically generalizable. To address this, and as a suggestion for future research, qualitative studies on sustainable entrepreneurship practices are recommended in this context. In addition, longitudinal studies may allow for a clearer monitoring of the development, benefits, and challenges associated with the implementation of sustainable practices over time.

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